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Research Paper

Formulation and Evaluation of Dexketoprofen Trometamol Loaded Extended Release Cubosomal Topical Gel

Aashish Singh^{*1}, Dr. Tanu Bhargava², Kamlesh Dashora³, Anju Tomar⁴

^{1,4}Institute of pharmacy, Vikram University, Ujjain

²Associate Professor, Institute of pharmacy, Vikram University, Ujjain

³Head of Department, Vikram University, Ujjain

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ABSTRACT

Objective-The research work comprises formulation and evaluation of cubosome as a potential drug loading carrier and extended release formulation. Dexketoprofen Trometamol is a NSAID drug used in some cases of acute pain and its formulation in cubosome hypothesizes that its entrapment efficiency is enhanced and there is also enhancement in its spread ability and to show extended release so that it may be easily used in topical formulations. **Method-** The cubosome was prepared by dispersion method. The method used was the method based on dispersion based on GMO, in which melted lipids are added drop-wise in aqueous medium at high temperature of about 80°C and at very high speed stirring of 6000-8000rpm followed by addition of ethyl alcohol. The mixture was stirred continuously and then polymer polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was added in drop-wise manner. Thus, A total of 5 formulations were prepared. **Result-** The formulated cubosome showed regular particle size ranging from 137-225nm (F2>F1>F3>F4>F5) and had a pH range of 6.3 to 6.7 which showed its slightly acidic nature. The different formulation showed drug entrapment ranging from 74.34%-80.50% (F2<F1<F3<F4<F5) and showed drug content from 62.14%-67.30% (F2<F3<F1<F4<F5). The formulations showed a fantastic spreadability capability of 8.12-9.37(F2<F3<F4<F1<F5). It was found that the percentage cumulative drug release of Dexketoprofen trometamol ranges from 79.24%-92.24% at 24-hour duration, in which formulation F5 showed maximum drug release of 92.24% while formulation F2 showed least release of 79.24%. **Conclusion-** After the formulation and evaluation of cubosomal gel prepared by dispersion-based technique we found that the formulation had sufficient entrapment capacity of drug into it. The drug content of prepared formulations found to be greater than conventional dosage form of the drug and also higher entrapment than other nanoparticles.

***Corresponding Author:** Aashish Singh

Address: Institute of pharmacy, Vikram University, Ujjain

Email ✉: aashishsingh2120@gmail.com

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In 5 formulations prepared the formulation F5 was better among all with greater drug content, greater drug entrapment and with lower particle size and a better spreadability. Thus, it was concluded that formulation F5 was optimized formulation. As conventional dosage form (tablet) of Dexketoprofen trometamol had shorter half-life (1.3hr) and having gastric irritability and higher first-pass metabolism the cubosome topical gel formulation of Dexketoprofen trometamol passes these drawbacks and showed extended drug release over 24 hour of time interval.

INTRODUCTION

Cubosome are liquid crystalline nanoparticle, the original observation of cubic liquid crystal comes in appearance during the study on polar lipids i.e. Monoolein, which are used as food stabilizer^{1, 2, 3}. Cubosome are discrete, nanostructured particles of bicontinuous cubic crystalline phase^{4, 5}. In this continuous phase a continuous lipid bilayer separates two water channels^{6, 7}. Cubosome are liquid but have solid crystal-like symmetry (cubic crystal-like symmetry). Cubosome are highly important in nanotechnology-based drug delivery⁵. Cubosome are derived from words 'cube' which means cubic in structure and prefixes with 'some' means phase⁹. Liquid crystals are intermediate states that have both solid and liquid properties¹⁰. They have molecular arrangement like solid and have flow property like liquids¹¹. Liquid crystals are mainly of two types –

- i. Thermotropic
- ii. Lyotropic (Cubosome)¹²

Cubosome comprise of curved lipid bilayer arranged in three-dimensional honeycomb-like structure that separates two internal aqueous channels with large interfacial area¹³. The term 'Cubosome' was coined by *Larsan*^{6,14,15}. The term Cubosome is USPTO (United states patent and trademark office) trademark for GS development AB corporation, Sweden¹⁶. Cubosome comes under category of ISA some (Internally self-assembled some – phases) they envelope inverse non-lamellar liquid crystalline phases¹⁷. Cubosome are biocompatible and biodegradable carrier due to their lipid phase. These are available as non-parenteral medication in UK while it is also included in USFDA list of guidelines for inactive ingredient¹⁸. Cubosome can accommodate three times the concentration of hydrophobic substances in it than traditional liposome. Appropriate 60% of outer surface of cubosome is in contact with water so it is highly suitable vehicle for delivering hydrophilic compounds¹⁸. Due to amphiphilic natured it can encapsulate various active molecules of different nature like hydrophilic, hydrophobic, Amphiphilic and Lipophilic¹⁹. Generally, cubosome size ranges from 100-300nm²⁰. Cubosome are usually composed of either unsaturated monoglyceride (GMO) or phytantrial because both forms bicontinuous cubic phase in water²¹.

ADVANTAGES:

Figure 01: -Flow chart diagram representing Advantages of Cubosome ³²

DISADVANTAGES

Figure 02: -Diagrammatic view of disadvantages of cubosome ³²

Application of Cubosome

In drug delivery-

- ✓ Oral route
- ✓ IV route
- ✓ Ophthalmic route
- ✓ Topical route
- ✓ Nasal route

As a drug carrier-

- ✓ Increased permeation
- ✓ Improve bioavailability
- ✓ Improve absorption
- ✓ Better bio-distribution

- ✓ Higher entrapment
- ✓ Better stability

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

Polymer glyceryl monooleate was purchased from Ases chemical works, Jodhpur. The drug Dexametoprolol Trometamol was provided by Emcure R&D gandhinagar, Gujrat as a free sample for my research work. Other chemicals like Ethanol, Poly vinyl alcohol and other ingredients were supplied by departmental chemical store.

Method

Drug- excipient interaction profile:

The drug and suitable excipients which are to be used in formulation are mixed and kept in a separate container for 45-60 days to watch that if there is change occurred in phase, color, odour or appearance of the mixture. If there was certain specific changing appears then the mixture is subjected to FTIR to analyze that if there is disturbance in reading that may affect the formulation.

METHOD OF CUBOSOME PREPARATION**Dispersion based on GMO: -**

The cubosome was prepared on dispersion based on Glycerol monooleate. The lipids to be used are melted according to their melting point mentioned. The melted lipids are then added to water at high temperature of about 80°C with continuous stirring so that an emulsion like preparation is prepared. The preparation is then placed into homogenizer for about 30min at 6000-8000rpm so that we got the preparation of suitable size range, Then the equilibrium of lipid and water is maintained and then it is to be added to the polymer polyvinyl alcohol.

Figure 03: - Chart showing preparation method of GMO based Dexketoprofen Trometamol Cubosome ³²

Table 01: - Formulation design of GMO based cubosome containing Dexketoprofen trometamol

S. No.	Formulation	GMO (mg)	PVA (ml)	Drug(mg)	Ethanol(ml)	Distil water(ml)
01.	F1	5ml	1.5ml	100mg	25ml	q.s
02.	F2	4ml	1ml	100mg	25ml	q.s
03.	F3	2.5ml	1ml	100mg	25ml	q.s
04.	F4	3ml	1.5ml	100mg	25ml	q.s
05.	F5	5ml	2.5ml	100mg	25ml	q.s

Evaluation Parameters of Cubosome

- i. Particle size
- ii. Surface topography
- iii. Ph
- iv. Drug content
- v. Entrapment efficiency
- vi. Thermal stability
- vii. Drug release rate through skin permeation
- viii. Drug release time

- 1) **Particle size and particle shape-** The mean particle size of Dexketoprofen Trometamol loaded cubosome was determined using an optical microscope. The microscope was fitted with a stage micrometer to calibrate the eyepiece micrometer. The particle size of formulated cubosome was determined using microscopy. Simple microscope under 100x resolutions was used to determine size of the

cubosome. The average particle size was determined using the following formula:

$$D\text{-mean} = \frac{\sum nd}{\sum n}$$

- 2) **Surface topography**- Surface topography and surface morphology was examined using high resolution scanning electron microscopy (HR-SEM) under resolution 100x to 5000x.
- 3) **Ph**- The ph of the formulation was determined using normal ph paper.
- 4) **Drug content**-1 g of prepared formulation containing drug equivalent to 10mg was extracted with 30ml of ethanol. The volume

$$\% \text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Actual concentration of drug in the formulation}}{\text{Theoractical concentration of drug}} \times 100$$

- 5) **Drug Entrapment Efficiency**-Accurately weighed quantity of prepared Dexketoprofen Trometamol loaded cubosome were taken and crushed in a mortar and pestle. 5ml of ethanol was added and transferred contents to a 100ml standard flask and made up to the volume with acetate buffer pH 5.5. Kept aside for 1h with frequent shaking for extracting the drug from the cubosome. Then it was filtered and the absorbance of filtrate was measured at 259nm after suitable dilutions. The drug content was calculated from the calibration curve and expressed as actual drug content in cubosome. The drug entrapment efficiency (%) of the cubosome was calculated according to following equation:

$$\text{DEE}\% = \frac{\text{Experiment drug loading}}{\text{Theoretical drug loading}} \times 100$$

- 6) **Thermal stability**-The thermal stability of formulation was determined using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). DSC measures heat flow associated with phase transitions and thermal events. The thermal efficiency of microsponge are analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The DSC

was made up to 100ml with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The solution was filtered. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 259nm using UV spectrophotometer after suitable dilutions. The drug content was determined by using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) with the help of UV spectrophotometer by dissolving the formulation in phosphate buffer for 24hrs and then sample was taken and analyzed in UV-spectrophotometer. The drug content of the formulation was determined using the following equation:

analysis was performed from temperature range of 0°C to 600°C and the effect of temperature was noted and graph was prepared to show chart of effect of temperature on enthalpy change of the formulations.

Procedure of differential scanning calorimetry:

- **Sample Preparation:** Place a small amount (1–10 mg) of the sample in an aluminum or standard pan; seal it properly. Leave an empty pan as a reference.
- **Instrument Setup:** Load both pans into the DSC instrument. Set the desired temperature range and heating/cooling rate.
- **Analysis:** The instrument heats or cools the pans, measuring the difference in heat flow between the sample and reference.
- **Data Interpretation**
 Detector Type: DSC-60
 Atmosphere: Nitrogen
 Gas Flow: 100 ml/min
 Pan Name: Aluminum
 Sample Weight: 5.000mg

- 7) **Spreadability**- spread ability is the measurement of time in seconds taken by two glass slides to slip off from gel which was placed in between the glass slides by applying

certain load. Less the time taken for the separation of two glass slides, better is the spread ability. 2g of the formulation was placed on a ground glass slide fixed on a wooden block. The gel formulation was sandwiched between this slide and the second slide having same dimensions. Second slide was provided with a hook. Measured quantity of weight (30g) was placed in a pan attached to the pulley with the help of hook. Time (in seconds) required by the top slide to separate from ground slide was noted. Shorter the interval, better the spreading coefficient.

8) Drug release from egg membrane- In- vitro release study of Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded Glycerol monooleate based cubosomal topical gel was carried out by using Franz diffusion cell. The formulation was taken in the donor compartment and Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was taken in the receptor compartment. The egg membrane, previously soaked overnight in the diffusion medium (Phosphate buffer pH 7.4) was placed between the donor

and receptor compartment. 1g of the Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded Glycerol monooleate based cubosomal topical gel was spread uniformly on the egg membrane, which is in contact with the receptor medium. The whole assembly was placed on the thermostatically controlled (constant temperature) magnetic stirrer with continuous stirring and the temperature of the medium was maintained at room temperature. At specific intervals, 2ml of sample was withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with an equal volume of Phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Absorbance of the sample was determined after suitable dilutions at 259nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Drug- Excipient interaction compatibility study of Dexketoprofen trometamol and GMO: -

The compatibility study of drug and excipient shows no interaction. The graph complies with the graph of standard graph of Dexketoprofen Trometamol.

Table 02: - IR frequencies of Dexketoprofen trometamol, Glycerolmonooleate, Ethanol and Polyvinyl alcohol

Functional group	Characteristic wave number	Wave number observed
CN stretching	2500-2400	2419.86
CH bending	1600-1400	1532.59
-C-	1300-1250	1273.12
enes	950-900	915.57

Figure 04: - FTIR spectrum of Dexketoprofen trometamol, Glycerol monooleate, Ethanol and Polyvinyl alcohol

Evaluation of Formulated Cubosome

1. Particle size: the mean particle size for different formulations of cubosome lays **137-225 nm.**, as shown in table no 03.

Figure 05: - Optical microscopic image of GMO cubosome containing Dexketoprofen trometamol

2. Surface topography using HR-SEM:

Figure 06: - HR-SEM image of GMO based Dexketoprofen trometamol cubosome under 100000 x Resolution

3. Ph of Cubosome: the ph of 5 formulations of cubosomes lie between **6.3 and 6.7**, which shows that the formulation were slightly acidic in nature.

Figure 07: - Bar graph showing Ph distribution of various formulations of Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosomes

4. Percentage drug content: The percentage drug content of GMO based cubosomes were found in between **62.14%- 67.30%**.

Figure 08: - Bar graph showing percentage drug content of 5 formulation of dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosome

5. Drug entrapment efficiency percentage: The percentage drug entrapment efficiency of formulations were found to be **74.34%-80.50%**.

Figure 09: - Bar graph showing percentage drug entrapment efficiency of Various formulations of dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosome

6. Spreadability: The spreadability of formulation F5 was highest with **9.37** and formulation F2 with lowest spread ability of **8.12**.

Figure 10: -Bar graph showing spreadability of formulations of dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosomal Gels

Table 03: - Table shows mean particle size, Ph, % Drug content and %DEE of different formulations of Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosomes

S No.	Formulation	Mean Particle size(nm)	Ph	%Drug content	%DEE	Spreadability (g.cm/sec)
01.	F1	183	6.4	65.30	76.90	9.10
02.	F2	225	6.7	62.14	74.34	8.12
03.	F3	178	6.4	65.90	76.60	8.55
04.	F4	166	6.5	66.25	79.25	8.82
05.	F5	137	6.3	67.30	80.50	9.37

Figure 11: - Bar graph showing pH, %Drug content, %DEE, Spreadability of Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosome Gel

7. Thermal stability:

Figure 12: - Graph showing Differential scanning calorimetry for cubosome

First baseline- 32°C
 Glass transition- 61-124°C
 Exothermic process- 225-290°C
 Crystallization phase- 225-290°C
 Endothermic process- 447-512°C
 Melting occur- 477°C
 Second baseline- 560°C - onward

8. Drug release from egg membrane (%cumulative drug release):-

The percentage cumulative drug release from different formulations of Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosome topical gel was observed by extracting egg membrane by using franz diffusion cell. The %CDR was analyzed for formulations at 24 hour time duration.

Table 04: - Chart showing percentage cumulative drug release (%CDR) of Dexketoprofen trometamol from its different formulations of cubosome

S.No.	Time (hr)	F1(%CDR)	F2(%CDR)	F3(%CDR)	F4(%CDR)	F5(%CDR)
01.	0	0	0	0	0	0
02.	01	9.02	6.84	8.70	9.89	10.90
03.	02	16.26	11.89	14.57	17.68	19.58
04.	04	24.41	18.68	21.03	26.86	28.38
05.	06	35.36	30.69	32.08	34.09	37.68
06.	08	43.10	39.04	40.68	42.89	43.62
07.	10	50.24	48.89	49.40	51.36	51.46
08.	12	58.83	54.68	56.80	57.35	58.98
09.	15	69.65	63.08	68.89	69.13	71.87
10.	18	76.52	72.93	75.65	78.37	80.65
11.	24	87.65	79.24	82.82	89.96	92.24

It was found that the percentage cumulative drug release of Dexketoprofen trometamol ranges from **79.24%-92.24%** at 24 hour duration, in which formulation F5 showed maximum drug release of

92.24% while formulation F2 showed least release of **79.24%**. Thus it was concluded that formulation F5 was optimized formulation.

Figure 13: - Graph showing percentage cumulative drug release of 5 formulations of Dexketoprofen trometamol loaded cubosomal topical gel**CONCLUSION:**

The research work aims to demonstrate the potential of this cubosomal nanoparticle as an effective treatment for acute pain with improved drug delivery. The research work comprises formulation and evaluation of cubosome as a potential drug loading carrier. There are many dosage forms like tablets and capsules available in the market for the treatment of inflammation, but still there is a need for new dosage forms which acts effectively. NSAIDs were mainly used for the treatment of Inflammation. Dexketoprofen Trometamol is a NSAID drug used in some cases of acute pain and its formulation in cubosome

hypothesizes that its entrapment efficiency is enhanced and there is also enhancement in its spread ability and also there is increment in drug release time so that it may be easily used in topical formulations. Cubosomes can be prepared by simple combination of biologically compatible lipids (GMO) and water and are thus more suited for pharmaceutical and body tissue. The formulated cubosome showed regular particle size ranging from 137-225nm (F2>F1>F3>F4>F5) and had a pH range of 6.3 to 6.7 which showed its slightly acidic nature. The different formulation showed drug entrapment ranging from 74.34%-80.50% (F2<F1<F3<F4<F5) and showed drug

content from 82.14%-87.30% (F2<F3<F1<F4<F5). The formulations showed a fantastic spreadability capability of 8.12-9.37(F2<F3<F4<F1<F5). We found that the formulation had sufficient entrapment capacity of drug into it. The drug content of prepared formulations found to be greater than conventional dosage form of the drug and also higher entrapment than other nanoparticles. In 5 formulations prepared the formulation F5 was better among all with greater drug content, greater drug entrapment and with lower particle size and a better spreadability. As conventional dosage form (tablet) of Dexketoprofen trometamol had shorter half life (1.3hr) and having gastric irritability and higher first-pass metabolism The cubosome topical gel formulation of Dexketoprofen trometamol passes these drawbacks and showed extended drug release over 24 hour of time interval with a magnificent drug release of upto 92.24%.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Nil

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